

SIMULTANEOUS ESTIMATION OF ISONIAZID AND METFORMIN HYDROCHLORIDE IN BULK BY USING UV SPECTROMETRIC METHOD.

Sawant Ramesh. L, **Tanpure Kallyani D***, Bharat Anjali V., Jadhav Kalyani A.

Pad. Dr. Vitthalrao Vikhe Patil Foundation's College of Pharmacy, Viladghat, Post MIDC, Ahamednagar, Maharashtra

Received on 28 – 12 - 2014

Revised on 13 – 01- 2015

Accepted on 24– 01 – 2015

ABSTRACT

Present work designed to develop UV spectrometric methods for antituberculosis and antidiabetic bulk drugs in combination. As moreover many diabetes patients those who suffering from tuberculosis can recovers simultaneously by both drugs(antituberculosis and antidiabetic).Hence there is need to develop methods for the simultaneous estimation of isoniazid and metformin hydrochloride. Two rapid and convenient UV spectrophotometric methods for simultaneous estimation of Isoniazid (INH) and Metformin hydrochloride(MET) in bulk with synthetic mixture have been developed by presenting two methods.The methods employed simultaneous equation method and absorbance ratio method for analysis of isoniazid and metformin. The work was carried out by using double beam JASCO U.V spectrophotometer with solvent methanol and selecting λ_{max} 260 nm for isoniazid and 234 nm for metformin. The regression coefficient for both drugs was found to be 0.995 and 0.993 for isoniazid and metformin respectively. The proposed methods were precise, accurate respectively.

Keywords: Isoniazid, Metformin HCL, Simultaneous equation, Absorbance ratio method

INTRODUCTION

Isoniazid chemically pyridine-4-carbohydrazide heterocyclic compounds which belongs to the pyridine carboxylic acids and derivatives. Isoniazid is the antitubercular drug and essential components of all antitubercular regimens unless the patient is not able to tolerate it or bacilli are resistant^(1,2). It is first line drug which can be called as primarily tuberculocidal.

Metformin hydrochloride is N,N-dimethylimido dicarbonimidic diamide hydrochloride a biguanide antihyperglycemic agent used for treating non-insulin-dependent diabetes mellitus. It improves glycemic control by decreasing hepatic glucose production, decreasing glucose absorption and increasing insulin mediated glucose uptake. Metformin is the only oral antihyperglycemic agent that is not associated with weight gain.

Structure of isoniazid and metformin shown in Fig1a & 1b.

Fig 1a:Structure of isoniazid

Fig 1b: Structure of metformin hydrochloride
Several assay techniques have been described for quantitative determination of isoniazid in HPLC, HPTLC, UV Spectrophotometry methods and bioanalytical methods. Few UV spectrophotometric methods HPLC and ion pair HPLC method have been reported for the estimation of metformin. As by the literature survey it was found that not a single method developed for INH and MET in combination. As both

drugs are official drug in I.P. and B.P. but no methods are reported for both in combination.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Reagents and Chemicals:

Bulk drugs isoniazid and metformin, methanol as a solvent and distilled water.

Instrumentation

Absorption spectral measurements were done out with Model-V630 Jasco double beam UV/Visible spectrophotometer with pair 10 mm matched quartz cells. Electronic balance(Model Shimadzu AUW-220D) used for weighing. Ultrasonicator model 5.5L150H was used for sonication.

Preparation of stock solution and standards:

Isoniazid and metformin 10 mg each were accurately weighed and transferred into 100 ml volumetric flask individually and small amount of methanol was added to dissolve drug. The volume was adjusted by solvent methanol upto the mark. The stock solution of isoniazid and metformin was prepared after making volume, which having concentration of drug 100 µg/ml. With the help of stock solution standard samples were prepared of 5,10,15,20,25,30 and 35 µg/ml respectively.

Selection of λ_{max} :

Standard samples of 20 µg/ml concentration of both INH and MET were scanned individually in the range of 200- 400 nm. λ_{max} was found to be 260 nm(λ_1) for INH and 234 nm(λ_2) for MET.

Methods I: Simultaneous equation method

Absorbance of the previously prepared standard solutions were measured at 260 nm and 234 nm for INH and MET respectively. At both λ_{max} , absorptivities (A 1%, 1cm) were determined for INH and MET. In the 5-35 µg/ml concentration range calibration curve were plotted. In the concentration range of 5-30 µg/ml for INH and 5-30 µg/ml for MET linearity was observed. The concentration of drugs in sample solution were determined by using the following formula.

Preliminary calculations and assumptions

1. The absorptivities of INH at λ_1 and λ_2 , a_{x1} and a_{x2} respectively.
2. The absorptivities of MET at λ_1 and λ_2 , a_{y1} and a_{y2} respectively.
3. The absorbance's of diluted sample at λ_1 and λ_2 , A_1 and A_2 respectively.
4. Let C_x and C_y be the concentrations of INH and MET respectively in diluted sample.

The two equations were constructed based upon the fact that at λ_1 and λ_2 the absorbance of the mixture is the sum of individual absorbance of INH and MET.

$$\text{At } \lambda_1, A_1 = a_{x1}c_x + a_{y1}c_y \dots (1)$$

$$\text{At } \lambda_2, A_2 = a_{x2}c_x + a_{y2}c_y \dots (2)$$

Where, A_1 and A_2 are absorbance of mixture at 262 nm and 234 nm respectivel

Method B: Absorbance ratio (Q – Absorbance) method.

Two wavelengths are selected for development of Q absorbance equation. It uses the ratio of absorbances at two selected wavelengths, one which is an isoabsorptive point and other being the λ -max of one of the two components. From the overlay spectra of two drugs, it is evident that INH and MET show an isoabsorptive point at 244 nm (A_1). The second wavelength used is 262 nm (A_2), which is the λ -max of INH. Concentrations of INH and MET were determined using following equations. The calibration curve was plotted at both wavelength.

The concentration of two drugs in the mixture can be calculated using following equations.

$$C_x = (Q_m - Q_y) \cdot A_1 / (Q_x - Q_y) \cdot a_{x1}$$

$$C_y = (Q_m - Q_x) \cdot A_1 / (Q_y - Q_x) \cdot a_{y1}$$

Where

$$Q_m = A_2 / A_1$$

$$Q_x = a_{x2} / a_{x1}$$

$$Q_y = a_{y2} / a_{y1}$$

Where, A_1 and A_2 are absorbance's of mixture at 244 nm and 262 nm respectively a_{x1} and a_{x2} are absorptivities of INH at λ_1 and λ_2 respectively and a_{y1} and a_{y2} are absorptivities of MET at λ_1 and λ_2 respectively. C_x and C_y are concentrations of INH and MET respectively.

Preparation and analysis of synthetic mixture:

From stock solution pipette out 1 ml of INH and MET solution each in 10 ml of volumetric flask and dilute with methanol to get 10 µg/ml of INH and MET solution. The absorbance of resulting solution taken at both λ max, submitting these values in equation we get concentration of drugs.

Validation:

The methods have validated according to ICH guidelines to study linearity, precision, Sensitivity, LOQ and LOD.

Linearity:

The linearity of measurement was evaluated by analyzing different concentrations of the standard solution of isoniazid and metformin. For both the methods, the Beer's law was obeyed in the concentration range 5-30µg/ml and 5-35µg/ml for INH and MET respectively. The correlation coefficient was found to be 0.995 at 260nm for isoniazid and 0.993 at 234nm for metformin.

Precision:

Precision of these methods was checked by analysing the samples at three different time intervals of the same day (intraday precision) as well as on different days (interday precision)

Limit of detection and limit of quantitation:

LOD and LOQ are calculated by using the values of slopes and intercepts of the calibration curves for both the drugs.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

The combination of isoniazid and metformin is play vital role in the treatment of patient suffering two disease at a time like diabetes and tuberculosis. Hence this present work provide very simple and accurate method for simultaneous estimation of antidiabetes and antituberculosis drugs. In simultaneous equation method, wavelengths selected for analysis were 260 nm for INH and 234 nm for MET. In Q-method, wavelength selected for analysis were 244nm. In both the methods linearity were observed in the concentration range of 5-30 µg/ml and 5-35 µg/ml for INH and MET, with good correlation coefficient 0.995 and 0.993 respectively. Both method are validated according to ICH guidelines all validation parameters were studied for the proposed method, like linearity, precision,sensitivity.

Table-1: Optical characteristics of isoniazid and metformin.

	Isoniazid	Metformin
Wavelength (nm)	260 nm	234 nm
Beer lambert's law limit (ug/ml)	5-30 µg/ml	5-30 µg/ml
Regression equation (y=mx+c)	Y = 0.071x+0.008	Y=0.092x+0.157
Slope (m)	0.071	0.092
Intercept (c)	0.008	0.157
Correlation coefficient (R ²)	0.995	0.993

Table no 2- Repeatability study of isoniazid for proposed method.

Conc. µg/ml	Simultaneous equation method		Q-absorbance ratio method	
	260 nm	234 nm	244 nm	260 nm
20	1.4334	0.851	1.175	1.4234
20	1.4321	0.851	1.174	1.4232
20	1.4334	0.854	1.176	1.4234
Mean	1.4329	0.852	1.175	1.4233
SD	0.00012	0.0031	0.0017	0.00137
%RSD	0.004	0.1033	0.0566	0.0456

Table-3- Repeatability study of metformin for proposed method.

Conc. µg/ml	Simultaneous equation method		Q-absorbance ratio method	
	234nm	260nm	244nm	260nm
20	1.990	1.212	1.1650	1.321
20	1.990	1.211	1.1653	1.322
20	1.991	1.212	1.1652	1.324
Mean	1.990	1.211	1.1651	1.322
SD	0.000707	0.0001	0.00017	0.0012
%RSD	0.0235	0.0033	0.0056	0.04

Table-4 – Intra-day and inter-day precision data for simultaneous equation method

Conc. (µg/ml)	Intra-day and inter-day precision data for isoniazid			
	Intra-day precision Absorbance		Inter-day precision Absorbance	
	260 nm	234 nm	260 nm	234 nm
10	0.3443	0.3161	0.3439	0.3159
15	0.6962	0.5052	0.6960	0.5052
20	1.1092	0.6943	1.1094	0.6942
Intra-day and inter-day precision data for metformin				
10	0.1166	0.541	0.1162	0.541
15	0.456	1.145	0.454	1.144
20	0.765	1.542	0.764	1.540

Table-5 – Intra-day and inter-day precision data for Q absorbance ratio method

Conc. (µg/ml)	Intra-day and inter-day precision data for the isoniazid			
	Intra-day precision Absorbance		Inter-day precision Absorbance	
	244 nm	260 nm	244 nm	260 nm
	10	0.3808	0.3442	0.3807
15	0.6479	0.6959	0.6479	0.6960
20	0.942	1.1090	0.939	1.1089
Intra-day and inter-day precision data for metformin				
10	0.4183	0.1162	0.4180	0.1164
15	0.6793	0.456	0.6792	0.459
20	0.9382	0.762	0.9383	0.765

Table-6- Limit of detection and limit of quantification

Parameters	Simultaneous equation method				Q-absorbance ratio method			
	Isoniazid		Metformin		Isoniazid		Metformin	
	260 nm	234 nm	260 nm	234 nm	244 nm	260 nm	244 nm	260 nm
LOD (µg/ml)	0.0557	0.1440	0.0253	0.00358	0.0790	0.063	0.00609	0.04304
LOQ (µg/ml)	0.1690	0.4366	0.0768	0.01086	0.2394	0.1929	0.01847	0.1304

Fig-2: Spectra of isoniazid API.

Fig-3: Spectra of metformin API.

Fig-4: Spectra of overlay spectra of isoniazid and metformin

Fig-5: Standard calibration plot of isoniazid in methanol.

Fig-6: Standard calibration plot of metformin in methanol.

CONCLUSION

The two spectrophotometric methods were developed and validated as per ICH guidelines. These validated methods are new, rapid, accurate, precise, sensitive, and reproducible. The standard deviation and % RSD calculated for the proposed methods are within limits, indicating high degree of precision of the methods. Hence, it can be concluded that the developed spectrophotometric methods are accurate, precise and can be employed successfully for the simultaneous estimation of isoniazid and metformin in bulk and formulation.

REFERENCES

- [1] www.isoniazid drugbank.com
- [2] K.D.Tripathi. *Essential of Medical Pharmacology*. Six Edition, 739-741.
- [3] www.metformin drugbank.com
- [4] Patil Sudharshan S.,Bonde C.G. Development and validation of analytical method for simultaneous estimation of glibenclamide and metformin hydrochloride in bulk and tablets using UV-Visible spectroscopy. *International Journal of Chem Tech Research*, Oct-Dec 2009 vol I;905-909.
- [5] *Indian Pharmacopiea*:4 Edition;vol 1,Controller of Publication,Delhi,1996
- [6] *British Pharmacopiea*,vol 1,British pharmacopiea commission,London,1993.
- [7] Arifa Begum S.K,Basava Raju.D and Rama Rao.N. Simultaneous estimation of rifampicin and Isoniazid in combined dosage form by a simple UV Spectrophotometric method. *Scholars Research Library* ISSN;419-426
- [8] S.K. Dhal &R. Sharma..Development and validation of RP-HPLC method for simultaneous determination of pyridoxine hydrochloride, isoniazid, pyrizinamid and rifampicin in pharmaceutical formulation. *Chem.Anal. (Warsaw)*,54 1487(2009).
- [9] Niraimathi vedhaiyan, Jerad suresh ayyadurai, Ramaprabha ramachandran, Senthil kumar irulappan. Visible spectrophotometric estimation of isoniazid in bulk and pharmaceutical dosage form. *International journal of pharmaceutical sciences review and research*;24(2), jan feb 2014 50-52
- [10] Depti Jain,Surendra Jain,Deepak Jain,and Manlik Amin:*Journal of chromatographic science* vol:4 july 2008.

